

Current Approaches to Peer Review

In an effort to align peer review with the general Open Science principles, open peer review (PR) is identified by seven key aspects: open identities, open reports, open participation, open interaction, open pre-review manuscripts, open final-version commenting, and open platforms.

* However, several **innovations to the PR process** have been characterized:

1. TRADITIONAL VS TRANSPARENT

In the most common model, reviewer anonymity allows for impartial decisions, uninfluenced by potential criticism from the authors. In double-anonymised PR, author anonymity limits reviewer bias pertaining to author's gender, country of origin, academic status, or previous publication history.

➔ The unsigned review reports are made available alongside the published article in transparent PR, where a response by the author may be included.

2. PRE VS POST-PUBLICATION

Pre-publication PR consists of a formal evaluation of research by editorially invited experts in the relevant field. Not to be confused with pre-PR commenting, which involves the informal commenting or discussion on a publicly available preprint.

➔ Post-publication PR is usually fully public and open, through the intermediation of sites such as Pubpeer—whistleblowing platforms that highlight shortcomings in papers, sometimes leading to retractions and accusations of scientific fraud.

3. STAGED

Results-blind PR is a counter-measure to publication bias, whereupon the results are firstly made unavailable to the reviewers, making the PR process similar to that of reviewing proposals by scientific grant agencies.

➔ It is an extension of registered reports (which are still restricted mainly to medical fields and psychology), where manuscripts are usually reviewed in two stages—the initial and most important review stage takes place after the study has been designed, but prior to data collection.

4. CROWDSOURCED

Sometimes, the reviewers interact online with the authors and other interested scientists for a more open and collaborative review. Collaborative review involves manuscript assessment wherein referees, editors, and external readers provide interactive comments leading to a consensus decision and a single set of revisions

➔ Cascading is now widely used, especially by larger publishing houses, and aims to avoid final rejection of a manuscript after peer review by redirecting critically reviewed manuscripts to potentially more suitable journals

5. DECOUPLED

Reports from commercial reviewer platforms can be used to assist in PR. For these portable reviews, the authors pay a company for a standard single-blind review that they can submit with the paper to collaborating journals.

➔ The post-publication evaluation of significant articles, often through a peer-nominated consortium, can also originate from recommendation services.